

EASY METHODS OF USING GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: Actually, there is an acute problem of increased psycho-emotional stress on students. The use of game forms of education helps to reduce information pressure on students. In the process of playing, a child imperceptibly seizes educational material. Many outstanding teachers rightly paid attention to the effectiveness of the use of games in the learning process. And this is understandable. We believe that the game manifests itself particularly fully and sometimes unexpectedly the abilities of a person, a child in particular. Games are highly motivating because they are amusing and interesting. In the aim of teaching students of different ages, teachers often face the problem of awakening activity in a lesson in children. Often there are situations when traditional forms of work do not contribute to the inclusion of students in the activities of the lesson and the emergence of their cognitive interest. Especially this problem in relation to the lessons of a foreign language is manifested when working with adolescents. If in elementary school the very method of conducting lessons involves the use of various funny songs, games, etc., then in adolescence, interest in these forms of work, of course, disappears and the choice of exciting learning techniques begins more complete. This article shows how games are highly motivating because they are amusing and interesting. Advantages of games in learning vocabulary are well-described and types of games are shown clearly in this article.

Key words: game, motivation, cognitive, affective, adaptability, entertaining, methodology, game, vocabulary, atmosphere, communicative, cohesion, communicative.

Language learning is hard work. Effort is required at every moment and must be maintained over a long period of time. Games help and encourage many learners to sustain their interest and work. A useful interpretation of 'meaningfulness' is that the learners respond to the content in a definite way. If they are amused, angered, intrigued or surprised the content is clearly meaningful to them. Thus the meaning of the language they listen to, read, speak and write will be more vividly experienced and, therefore, better remembered.

One of the best ways of doing this is through games. There are many advantages of using games in the classroom:

1. Games are a welcome break from the usual routine of the language class.

2. They are motivating and challenging.
3. Learning a language requires a great deal of effort. Games help students to make and sustain the effort of learning.
4. Games provide language practice in the various skills- speaking, writing, listening and reading.
5. They encourage students to interact and communicate.
6. They create a meaningful context for language use.

Actually, there is an acute problem of increased psycho-emotional stress on students. The use of game forms of education helps to reduce information pressure on students. In the process of playing, a child imperceptibly seizes educational material. Many outstanding teachers rightly paid attention to the effectiveness of the use of games in the learning process. And this is understandable. We believe that the game manifests itself particularly fully and sometimes unexpectedly the abilities of a person, a child in particular.

The school occupies a special place such forms of employment, which provide active participation in the lesson of each student, increase the authority of knowledge and individual responsibility of students for the results of educational work.

The game is a specially organized activity that requires tension of emotional and mental strength. The game always involves making a decision - what to do, what to say, how to win? The desire to solve these issues sharpens the mental activity of the players. Are there rich learning opportunities here? Children, however, do not think about it. For them, the game above all - an exciting experience. Therefore, in our opinion, the goal of the game form of education is not only the formation of pronunciation, lexical and grammatical skills, but also the development of interest in the language being studied.

Games also lend themselves well to revision exercises helping learners recall material in a pleasant, entertaining way. All authors referred to in this article agree that even if games resulted only in noise and entertained students, they are still worth paying attention to and implementing in the classroom since they motivate learners, promote communicative competence, and generate fluency. Games have been shown to have advantages and effectiveness in learning vocabulary in various ways. First, games bring in relaxation and fun for students, thus help them learn and retain new words more easily. Second, games usually involve friendly competition and they keep learners interested. These create the motivation for learners of English to get involved and participate actively in the learning activities. Third, vocabulary games bring real world context into the classroom, and enhance students' use of English in a flexible,

communicative way. Therefore, the role of games in teaching and learning vocabulary cannot be denied. However, in order to achieve the most from vocabulary games, it is essential that suitable games are chosen. Whenever a game is to be conducted, the number of students, proficiency level, cultural context, timing, learning topic, and the classroom settings are factors that should be taken into account.

The role of the game in the learning process

I would like to highlight the purpose of using games in foreign language lessons. There are six main goals:

1. the formation of certain skills;
2. the development of certain speech skills;
3. learning to communicate;
4. development of the necessary abilities and mental functions;
5. cognition (in the sphere of the formation of the language itself);
6. memorization of speech material.

The game is important for personal development also because during the course of its development a lesson situation is created in which the student involved in the competition really wants to help his team, tries to find the right answer, is active. As experience shows, such situations allow one to express oneself not only to strong but also weak students. Very often, students who are not distinguished by good performance can show themselves here from a completely different perspective and become active participants in the game, contribute to the victory of their team. Using games from this point of view can be an important success factor for weak children, arouse their interest in the subject, and become the basis for their subsequent success in studying it.

But the specifics of the game is that “learning tasks appear before a child not in an explicit form, but disguised. While playing, the child does not set a learning task, but as a result of the game he learns something.” There is no need or reason to set a goal - to rest, to switch: the nature of the game as such will do its work. As an experience of teachers and theorists shows, one of the effective methods of teaching, the use of which makes a foreign language a favorite subject of schoolchildren.

Games-exercises. They usually take 10-15 minutes and are aimed at improving the cognitive abilities of students, are a good tool for the development of cognitive interests, understanding and consolidating educational material, applying it in new situations. This is a variety of quizzes, crosswords, puzzles, charades, puzzles, the explanation of proverbs and sayings, riddles.

Travel Games. They can be carried out both directly in the classroom and in the process of extracurricular activities. They serve mainly the purposes of deepening, understanding and consolidating educational material. Activation of students in travel games is expressed in oral stories, questions, answers, in their personal experiences and judgments.

The storyline (role-playing) game is different from exercise games and travel games in that the conditions of an imaginary situation are simulated, and the students play certain roles.

A competition game may include all the above-mentioned types of didactic games or their individual elements. To conduct this type of game, students are divided into groups, teams, between which there is a competition. The essential feature of the competitive game is the presence of competitive struggle and cooperation in it [1].

In the process of working with students, the teacher can develop cognitive games himself and test their effectiveness in practice. When organizing games, I use the following principles:

- 1) fascination
- 2) team or group work
- 2) differentiated approach
- 4) using modern information technologies

As examples, presented are the development of three games for students in grades 5-7 : **Word-searchgrid**

FIND AMONG THE LETTERS OF THE WORD ON THE TOPIC "MONEY"

C	U	R	R	E	N	C	Y	R	B	Q	U	A	S
A	X	S	D	N	U	F	N	I	A	U	B	C	F
S	I	L	V	E	R	H	N	C	N	I	O	C	E
H	O	F	U	N	D	S	E	H	K	P	T	O	E
G	C	H	A	N	G	E	P	U	R	S	E	U	R
C	H	E	Q	U	E	Y	M	S	K	R	W	N	I
E	R	A	M	D	I	N	T	E	R	E	S	T	A
N	S	D	O	U	P	Z	A	T	A	R	H	F	N
U	E	V	A	S	S	K	X	O	M	U	O	F	O
T	H	A	M	D	N	E	Y	N	F	S	P	O	I
R	E	S	N	P	R	I	C	E	Y	A	P	L	L
O	S	U	P	L	S	P	E	N	D	E	I	L	L
F	O	W	E	A	L	T	H	A	U	R	N	E	I
P	T	N	E	M	E	T	A	T	S	T	G	W	M

WRITE A TRANSLATION NEXT TO A WORD

_____ cash _____ mark _____ save _____ tax _____
 _____ currency _____ pay _____ pound _____ notes _____
 _____ change _____ gold _____ coin _____ fort _____

une _____ silver _____ treasure _____ well-off _____
_____ spend _____ funds _____ wealth _____ rich _____
_____ statement _____ price _____ money _____ inter
est _____ purse _____ shopping _____ account _____
_____ bank _____ cheque _____ fee _____
_____ millionaire _____ penny _____.

2. The game "Detective Story".

Purpose: working out general and special questions in Past Simple. The teacher says: "Yesterday afternoon, a bank robbery was committed. Suspected two. Two students go out into the corridor and agree on an alibi for yesterday. The remaining guys are investigators. They call (one by one) the detainees and interrogate them (ask questions), try to prove their guilt and that their alibi is fictional. Questions may be: Did you go to the shop in the afternoon yesterday? What did you do at three o'clock yesterday? Etc.

3. The game "What am I going to do?"

Purpose: working out the structure to be going to do. As soon as the teacher crossed the threshold of the class, he stopped and asked, "What am I going to do now?" The students looked at the teacher questioningly and were surprised at the beginning of the lesson.

Student 1: "You are going to the classroom."

Teacher: "Oh! No! I'm not going to the classroom. I'm already in the classroom. But what am I going to do? Am I going to sleep? Am I going to eat? What am i going to do? "

Student 1: "You are going to give us a lesson."

Teacher: "Yes, quite right. I am going to teach you. Now I am taking a piece of chalk. What am i going to do now? "

Student 2: "You are going to write."

Teacher: "Yes, that's right. Oh! It's very hot here. Now I'm near the window. What am i going to do? "

Student 3: "You are going to open the window."

Teacher: "Right. Now I have taken a pen and opened register."

Student 4: "You are going to mark the absentees."

Teacher: "Try to guess what I'm going to do." (Children show what they are going to do.)

Games in Small Groups

There are also lots of games that can be played in groups of about four students.

- *Board games* where students move pieces and answer questions or form

sentences based on images make for good practice activities. For practicing the “If ~, then ~.” structure a Chutes and Ladders layout may be fun for students. - *Card games* such as Go Fish, Memory, and many more can be adapted for classroom use. When you are **teaching comparatives**, card games can be an invaluable tool. You can also use simple card games to test comprehension by making up decks of cards with letters for example. Have students spread all the cards face up on their desks, you then say a letter aloud, and the first student to slap the correct card gets to keep it. Repeat until all the cards are gone and the student with the most cards at the end of the game wins. To make this more challenging, you can tell students that if they slap the wrong card, they have to take one card out of their pile.

Paiwork Games

There are many of pair activities students can do to practice English but very few of them take the form of a game. - *The best and most versatile one by far is Battleship*. This will take a lesson to explain and practice but once your students are familiar with it, can be played as a twenty to thirty minute activity. Battleship is best used **to practice tenses**. The worksheet consists of two identical seven by seven grids, one above the other. The first box in the upper left is kept blank, the first row is filled in with phrases such as “play soccer” and “study English”, and the first column is filled in with words such as “I, You, He, We, They, The students.” Students should secretly draw their “boats” on the grid. Typically one boat should have five squares, one boat should have four squares, two boats should have three squares, and one boat should have two squares. Boats can only be drawn vertically or horizontally. On the board practice the structure that students will use for the activity for example “I played soccer. You studied English.” until every row and column has been practiced and then instruct students to say “Hit”, “Miss”, or “You sank my ship!” when appropriate just like in the original game. Students can usually play two or three times before moving on to another activity.

CONCLUSION

Game methods are one of the most effective methods of teaching a foreign language, since their psychological and pedagogical basis is play activity, which makes a great contribution to the mental development of an individual. The use of gaming techniques in foreign language lessons in high school meets the cognitive needs of adolescents. The game activates thought processes and increases the motivation to learn a foreign language.

Learning a foreign language vocabulary is a process that covers several stages. At the first stage, a new word is introduced. At the next stage, students

are trained in creating lexical speech connections in the same type of speech situations. The result of training is the ability of students to create dynamic lexical speech communication, that is, to freely use new words in communication.

Game forms and techniques are very diverse and can be used at every stage of working with vocabulary. At the first stages, it is appropriate to use typical game exercises that will make the process of memorizing words an interesting exercise. Game methods allow you to create very real situations of communication between participants in the game. Therefore, games are particularly relevant in the **final. The game method may be used at any stage of studying with a specific adaptation for each age. Using this method is called to create a favourable psychological atmosphere of communication and to help students see the foreign language as a real means of communication. It is therefore important that lessons using gaming techniques have become for the students a pleasant experience. This can be achieved if properly and methodically psychologically reasonable to work to find ways of optimal organization of lessons in a foreign language. It should be noted that the use of games in various stages of training not only helps in learning a foreign language, but also plays a role in the transition of the student to a new and higher stage of mental development stages of working with new vocabulary, in which words are used in speech in specific game situations.**

Game teaching methods are diverse. Depending on the pedagogical goals, methods of organization, level of language proficiency, several groups of games are distinguished. Plot-role-playing and intellectual, for example, require a high knowledge of vocabulary, as they imply spontaneous utterances of players. Games can be presented in the form of game elements, situations, exercises, and be directed to other goals. Game methods vary depending on the number of participants, time, and so on.

Game methods are often very simple in their organization and do not require special equipment. Game methods can be used in each lesson of a foreign language, as long as they correspond to the goals and objectives of the training. This work presents game exercises that actualize knowledge of the vocabulary on the topic and game situations with which the situations of communication were created in the lesson. These gaming techniques were successfully carried out in practice.

Questionnaires allow us to conclude that there is a comfortable situation in the lessons where game methods were used. The chosen method of conducting

classes contributes to the improvement of the quality of knowledge, worldview, and most importantly, the students are interested in cognitive activity.

Thus, we can conclude that the hypothesis proposed in the paper that the use of the game in the educational process allows an increase in the activity of students' cognitive activity.

In conclusion, **Current methods of using games in teaching English** is one effective and interesting way that can be applied in any classrooms. The results of this research suggest that games are used not only for mere fun, but more importantly, for the useful practice and review of language lessons, thus leading toward the goal of improving learners' communicative competence.

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